

ANALYSIS OF IR 4.0 ADOPTION IN AUTOMOTIVE WELDING SHOP

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Industry 4.0 refers to the fourth industrial revolution, which affects every manufacturing domain and comprises advanced manufacturing technologies that capture, optimize, and deploy data. In other words, Industry 4.0 makes factories “smart” by implementing such technologies as the industrial Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, and cyber-physical systems interact seamlessly, communicating and adjusting continuously. Businesses that fully understand and capture the value of these advantages will be best positioned to take on the challenges that lie ahead [1].

In order to evaluate IR 4.0 readiness for manufacturing and operation, self-assessment tool established by University of Warwick is used. The assessment comprises 4 main elements – technology integration, autonomous workplace, data management and resource capability [2]. As shown in Table 1, 3 welding plant are included in this assessment for study purpose. The score for each element ranging from 1 (beginner level) to 4 (expert level).

Key Area	Items	Plant (Welding Shop)		
		Plant A	Plant B	Plant C
Technology Integration	Automation	3	3	1
	M2M - Machine & operation integration	3	3	3
Autonomous Workplace	Self - optimise process	1	1	4
	Autonomous guided vehicle / workpiece	1	3	1
Data management	Operation data collection	3	3	1
	Operation data usage	2	2	2
	Cloud solution usage	2	2	1
	IT & data security	3	3	1
Resource Capability	Digital modelling	2	2	1
	Equipment readiness for Industry 4.0	3	2	3
Total Score		23	24	18

Table 1

Then, using radar chart, the assessment’s summary is plotted for comparison (Figure 2). Since energy efficiency or renewable energy is not considered as one of assessment criteria, the usage of solar panel to generate electricity for Plant A is put on the note. In addition, Plant A is used as base line for comparison with other plant.

Figure 2

Base on Figure 2, under 'Autonomous Workplace' element, Plant B and C are much better than Plant A. Plant B implements automated guided vehicle (AGV) to transfer parts from closures to fitting line since part supply using 'Set – Part – Supply' (SPS) method. Plant C implements adaptive spot welding system in which the controller will automatically adjust welding current or weld time base on recorded dynamic resistance curve to compensate disturbance during welding operation such as bad fitting of the sheets, shunting, variation of coating and welding force. Moreover, all the actual welding parameters are been recorded automatically in the system.

Base on study conducted by Fraunhofer Institute of Manufacturing Engineering and Automation (Roland Berger), the estimated cost saving resulted from IR 4.0 adoption is between 10% to 20% as shown in Figure 3. One major factor driving improvement in manufacturing will be increasingly advanced robotics or machinery, as technologies such as self-reconfiguring machines and the human-robot collaboration of "cobotics" become increasingly mainstream [3].

Figure 3

This study is quite important as guideline or reference when upgrading any equipment or system in order to not overspending money for IR 4.0 adoption. Therefore, the realistic value to spend for upgrading is between 10% to 15% additional cost from initial purchase value of the equipment or system. This is to ensure shorten return of investment (ROI) time and maximize profit.

Another representation of IR 4.0 scope for smart factory is by Advantech, which is simpler and easy to relate with current automotive welding shop since it only focus on main operation inside factory. As shown on figure 4, 5 main elements or system that can be integrated together to form adaptive and connected factory which are – MES and production profile, production testing equipment, machine automation, predictive maintenance and factory environmental monitoring [4].

Figure 4

Based on these elements, the same 3 welding plant are evaluated for comparison and system upgrading proposal for IR 4.0 adoption. As shown in Table 5, another 2 elements need to be improved for Plant A and B – production testing equipment and predictive maintenance. All plant comply for factory environmental monitoring since this is one of key elements to reduce operational cost especially on electric and water consumption. Energy consumption on each plant must be closely monitored to improve the efficiency [5].

Key Area / System	Plant (Welding Shop)		
	A	B	C
MES and Production Profile (including OEE)	Green	Green	Yellow
Production Testing Equipment	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Machine Automation	Green	Green	Yellow
Predictive Maintenance	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
Factory Environmental Monitoring	Green	Green	Green

Table 5

The system upgrading proposal for Plant A and B is shown in figure 6 [6]. In order to improve predictive maintenance element, the existing robot controller can be upgraded into remote service which offers online monitoring and troubleshooting capability [7]. Lastly, for production testing element, new online measurement for body accuracy and fitting (gap and flushness) can be proposed for implementation.

Figure 6

In summary, in order to adapt IR 4.0, detail analysis on cost must be done since base on study by Roland Berger, the estimated manufacturing operation cost saving is from 10% to 20% only. Therefore, the top priority must go for improving energy management system such as using solar panel to generate electricity because this will greatly reduce manufacturing operation cost between 40% to 60%. Another option to reduce cost is by implementing Robot/Equipment- as-a- Service. Same as computer and photocopy machine services, rather than purchasing the equipment which require additional maintenance cost during operation, rental concept is preferable and this concept is suitable for high mix, short batch and frequent changeover in production operation [8]. However, this concept is still new and require time for equipment maker or integrator to do preparation.

References

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